

Substituent Directed Oxidative Cyclisation. Application to the Synthesis of Natural Products[†]

S. CHANDRASEKARAN

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur-208 016

In the last few years we have been interested in the development of new synthetic methodologies for a variety of chemo-, regio-, and stereoselective transformations. In this presentation I shall try to give an account of our studies related to substituent directed oxidative cyclisation with oxochromium and oxomanganese based reagents.

In the course of our synthetic work at one stage we needed a good method for the vicinal dihydroxylation of a carbon-carbon double bond. The most common method generally employed is the reaction of the olefin either with stoichiometric amount of osmium tetroxide¹ or with catalytic amount of osmium tetroxide with a co-oxidant such as *N*-methylmorpholine *N*-oxide². Permanganate derived reagents have not been employed with success for effecting this transformation due to undesirable over-oxidation. Quaternary ammonium permanganates like benzyltriethylammonium permanganate³ and tetra-*n*-butylammonium permanganate⁴ have been used for other oxidative transformations but were found to be ineffective for *cis*-dihydroxylation of olefins. Use of quaternary ammonium permanganates in organic synthesis is also restricted because of the violent explosions encountered in their use⁵. In the course of our search for a cheaper, better and safer quaternary ammonium permanganate, we found that cetyltrimethylammonium permanganate (CTAP)⁶ (1) is the ideal reagent which would effect *cis*-hydroxylation of a variety of olefins at 0–15° in 2–4 h under anhydrous conditions (Scheme 1).

Two key features of this methodology are: (i) the diol (3) which is a product of *cis*-hydroxylation of 2 does not undergo further oxidation with excess of cetyltrimethylammonium permanganate (CTAP) (1) and (ii) allylic alcohols (like 8) do not undergo either *cis*-hydroxylation of the carbon-carbon double bond or oxidation of the secondary hydroxyl group.

Although simple primary or secondary hydroxylic groups are not affected by CTAP, the compounds containing benzylic hydroxyl groups undergo a smooth and highly selective oxidation to give the corresponding carbonyl compounds (Scheme 2)⁷.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Salient features of this methodology are (i) benzaldehyde (12) which is a product of oxidation of benzyl alcohol (11) does not undergo further oxidation to carboxylic acid under the reaction conditions and (ii) compound 13 on oxidation gives 14

[†] Basudev Banerjee Memorial Lecture (1987) delivered under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society on December 25, 1988 at Calcutta.

in high yield where only the benzylic hydroxyl group is selectively oxidised in the presence of a non-benzylic hydroxyl group in the molecule. Having shown the utility of CTAP (1) in two key reactions, it was decided to explore the scope and limitations of this oxomanganese reagent in other oxidative transformations.

Earlier work from our laboratories has shown that treatment of tertiary γ - and δ -hydroxy olefins with pentavalent chromium reagent, (BipyH₂)CrOCl₂⁸ affords very good yields of the corresponding γ - and δ -lactones⁹. A number of spiro and bicyclic lactones have been synthesised using this methodology (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

Surprisingly, the same transformation could also be accomplished with chromium(vi) reagents like pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC)⁹ and with chromium trioxide in acetic acid/acetic anhydride¹⁰. Although both the methodologies mentioned above work well in the case of tertiary hydroxy olefins, they are not synthetically useful for oxidative cyclisation of primary or secondary γ - and δ -hydroxy olefins. For example, oxidation of 15 and 18 with chromium(v) reagent gives only poor yield of the lactones 16 and 19, respectively, the major product being the corresponding carbonyl compounds 17 and 20 (Scheme 4). The oxidative cyclisation of ω -hydroxy olefins with oxochromium(vi) reagents like PCC is not straightforward and is provocative from a mechanistic point of view.

Scheme 4

Application of the oxochromium reagents based methodology for oxidative cyclisation of tertiary- γ -hydroxy olefins have been exemplified with the synthesis of (\pm) dihydroactinidiolide (21)^{9b,11}, a pheromone component of red fire ant (Scheme 5), dihydrojasnone^{9,12} (Scheme 6) and (\pm) nor-bisabolide (23)¹³ (Scheme 7).

Scheme 5

Scheme 6

Scheme 7

It was felt that if the oxidative cyclisation methodology can be applied to the synthesis of γ - and δ -lactones in good yield from primary or secondary hydroxy olefins, this would prove to be extremely useful. Unlike other permanganate derived reagents, our newly developed cetyltrimethylammonium permanganate (CTAP) (1) does not oxidise primary and secondary alcohols and therefore it appeared worthwhile to explore the usefulness of CTAP (1) for effecting oxidative cyclisation of ω -hydroxy olefins.

Accordingly, when treated with two molar equivalents of CTAP (1) in CH_2Cl_2 or CHCl_3 ($25-50^\circ$) we find that primary, secondary and tertiary γ - and δ -hydroxy olefins undergo oxidative cyclisation with the loss of a carbon atom to give γ - and δ -lactones, respectively, in good yields¹⁴. The scope of this methodology can be easily gauged from the variety of substrates indicated in Scheme 8. The oxidation of compounds 45 and 46 (Scheme 9) is particularly interesting since they are derived from the same allyl chloride (44) via Grignard reaction under different conditions¹⁵ and lead to two different γ -lactones 42 and 47, respectively, in good yield¹⁴.

This oxidative cyclisation of γ -hydroxy olefins with oxochromium and oxomanganese reagents is

Scheme 8

Scheme 9

clearly substituent (hydroxyl) directed oxidative cyclisation. This conclusion is supported by the fact that if the hydroxyl group is protected as in **48** or **49**, the corresponding γ -lactones are not formed by oxidative cyclisation¹⁶ (Scheme 10).

Scheme 10

Application of oxidative cyclisation methodology to natural product synthesis :

Synthesis of (\pm)-eldanolide, the insect sex pheromone of the sugar cane borer, Eldana saccharina¹⁷ : The Grignard reagent derived from prenyl chloride (**44**) in the presence of 10% CuI was treated with 4-pentenal (**51**) to get the crucial intermediate **52** (74%) for oxidative cyclisation. Oxidation of **52** with CTAP at 25° for 3 h resulted in the formation of the γ -lactone (**53**; 62%). α -Phenylselenation followed by selenoxide elimination¹⁸ yielded the α,β -unsaturated lactone (**54**; 72%). Stereospecific conjugate addition of lithium dimethyl cuprate to **54** afforded (\pm)-eldanolide (**55**; 65%) (Scheme 11)¹⁷.

Synthesis of cis-syn-cis-tricyclo[6.3.0.0^{2,6}]undecane carbon skeleton¹⁹ : We reported an efficient application of the oxidative cyclisation strategy in an iterative approach to set up the basic skeleton of a *cis-syn-cis*-tricyclo[6.3.0.0^{2,6}]undecane carbon skeleton. It is anticipated that easy accessibility to **61** and its derivatives would open up new possibilities for further synthetic exploitation. Accordingly, reaction of cyclopentanone with Grignard reagent derived from 4-bromo-1-butene²⁰ gave the alcohol (**35**; 62%) which was then subjected to oxidative cyclisation with CTAP to yield the spiro-lactone (**40**^{14,21}; 71%). Treatment of the lactone (**40**) with phosphorous pentoxide in methane sulphonic acid²² for 2 h at 50° led to the rearranged bicyclic enone (**56**²³; 98%). Hydrogenation of **56** with Pd/C produced the saturated *cis*-bicyclic ketone (**57**²⁴; 99%). To continue the synthesis the bicyclic ketone **57** was subjected to the same sequence of reactions. Thus, condensation with the Grignard reagent produced the adduct **58** (64%). Oxidative cyclisation with CTAP afforded the spiro-lactone (**59**; 60%). Rearrangement of **59** with phosphorous pentoxide/methane sulphonic acid yielded the tricyclic enone (**60**; 92%). Catalytic hydrogenation of **60** with Pd/C resulted in the *cis*-addition of hydrogen to the less hindered face of the olefin to give the product **61** (98%) (Scheme 12)¹⁹.

Synthesis of optically active γ -lactone intermediate 64 : Brooks²⁵ had earlier shown that the optically active alcohol (**63**) can be obtained from the prochiral

Scheme 12. Reagents: (i) $\text{BrMgCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}=\text{CH}_2$, (ii) CTAP, CH_2Cl_2 , (iii) $\text{P}_2\text{O}_5-\text{MeSO}_3\text{H}$, (iv) $\text{Pd/C}, \text{H}_2$.

ketone (62) via a highly enantio-selective and diastereoselective microbial reduction with baker's yeast. Compound 63 has been converted to the optically active lactone in a three-step sequence. In the present study we have been able to effect a one-step oxidative cyclisation of 63 with CTAP to the optically active lactone (64)²⁵ (Scheme 13).

Scheme 13

Oxidative transformations of 1,5-dienes with modified permanganate reagents: Klein and Rojahn²⁶, Walba²⁷ and Baldwin²⁸ studied the oxidative addition of alkaline potassium permanganate to 1,5-dienes. The reaction of three isomeric 2,6-octadienes 65, 66 and 67 have been shown to give the tetrahydrofuran derivative 68, 69 and 70, respectively, with high degree of stereospecificity albeit in low yields (Scheme 14)²⁷.

Scheme 14

Since our quaternary ammonium permanganate, CTAP (1) has turned out to be quite different in its reactivity towards a variety of functional groups,

it was of interest to study its reaction with 1,5-dienes. We were also interested in studying the reaction of 1,5-dienes with permanganate ion under heterogeneous conditions.

Surprisingly, 1,5-hexadiene (71) on treatment with excess CTAP at 0–10° resulted in the formation of hydroxymethylbutyrolactone (73) with a loss of a carbon atom. On the other hand, treatment of 71 with 1.1 equiv. of CTAP gave the diol (72). Reaction of potassium permanganate impregnated on $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ²⁹ with 71 in dichloromethane also resulted in the formation of the lactone (73; 32%) (Scheme 15)²⁹.

Scheme 15

Similarly, reaction of geranyl acetate (74) or neryl acetate (75) under heterogeneous oxidation conditions with potassium permanganate impregnated on copper sulphate yielded the same keto lactone (77) in good yield. However, reaction of 74 with excess CTAP yielded only the hydroxy lactone (76). These results are not altogether surprising since CTAP does not oxidise primary or secondary hydroxyl function whereas $\text{KMnO}_4/\text{CuSO}_4$ system is known to oxidise secondary alcohols selectively²⁹. Oxidation of 76 with PCC afforded the keto lactone (77; Scheme 16)³⁰.

Scheme 16

Thus, the reaction of 1,5-dienes with modified permanganate reagents result in the formation of substituted γ -butyrolactones with the loss of one or more carbon atoms. It is possible to visualise these reactions also as substituent (hydroxyl) directed oxidative cyclisation of γ -hydroxy olefins.

Possible mechanistic pathways for substituent directed oxidative cyclisation with oxochromium and

oxomanganese reagents : As seen earlier this reaction is clearly substituent (hydroxyl) directed oxidation and there are two closely related mechanistic pathways which can account for the formation of the products. One pathway for the oxidative cyclisation of γ -hydroxy olefins like **34** (where the olefin is unsubstituted) with oxochromium results is delineated in Scheme 17⁸¹.

The first step in the mechanism is the formation of a π -complex of the oxochromium reagent with the olefin (**34**) which is subsequently attacked by the hydroxyl substituent to yield the chromate ester (**78**). This proposal is very similar to the one invoked by Herz⁸² in explaining the oxidative rearrangement of allylic alcohols with chromium(VI) reagents. It is likely that the chromate ester decomposes to give the aldehyde (**79**) which is in equilibrium with the enol (**79a**) and can easily undergo oxidative cleavage to give the γ -lactone (**39**) and formic acid. Partial support for this mechanism comes from the following observations. When the reaction of **34** with PCC was performed under controlled conditions (25°, 10 h) apart from unreacted **34** and lactone **39**, aldehyde **79** (15%) was isolated. Compound **79** when treated again with excess PCC got converted completely to the lactone (**39**) showing thereby that the aldehyde (**79**) is likely to be an intermediate in the overall transformation.

A closely related mechanism is postulated for the oxidative cyclisation of γ -hydroxyolefins like **80** where the olefin is substituted (Scheme 18)⁸¹. Initial complexation with the oxochromium(VI) followed by hydroxyl directed cyclisation can lead to the chromate ester (**80a**) which hydrolyses to give the tertiary alcohol (**81**). Dehydration of **81** under the reaction conditions may lead to the enol ether (**82**). Oxidative cleavage of the enol ether (**82**) will result in the formation of the lactone (**39**). This mechanism is also partly supported by the observation that treatment of **80** with PCC under controlled conditions (25°, 8 h) led to the isolation of the alcohol (**81**) as one of the products apart from unreacted **80** and lactone **39**. This alcohol (**81**) when treated separately with PCC resulted in the formation of the lactone (**39**). Although enol

Scheme 18

ether (**82**) could not be isolated from the reaction mixture either in the reaction of **80** or **81** with PCC, **82** synthesised by an independent route underwent smooth oxidative cleavage with pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC) to give **39**. The mechanisms that we have suggested account for most of our observations and throw some light on the substituent directed oxidative cyclisation of γ -hydroxyolefins.

Oxidation of substituted enol ethers with oxochromium reagents⁸⁴ : Piancatelli⁸³ showed that cyclic and acyclic enol ethers on treatment with pyridinium chlorochromate yield lactones and esters, respectively (Scheme 19). This reaction is

believed to proceed via the formation of a cyclic chromate ester (**84**) which decomposes by 1,2-hydride shift to yield the lactone (**85**). We anticipated that if the enol ether is highly substituted and devoid of hydrogen for hydride transfer, the intermediate cyclic chromate ester would decompose by cleavage of the carbon-carbon bond. As expected enol ethers **88**, **90** and **91** on treatment with PCC at 25° for 1 h gave the carbonyl compounds **89**, **43** and **16**, respectively, in very high yields (Scheme 20)⁸⁴.

The fact that the reaction turns out to be an extremely useful methodology for the highly selective oxidative cleavage of enol ethers under mild reactions is illustrated with the synthesis of substituted butanolides (Scheme 21)²⁶. For example,

Scheme 21

linalool (92) was subjected to bromoetherification with NBS to give 93 which on treatment with potassium t-butoxide gave the exocyclic enol ether (94)²⁶. Oxidation of 94 with PCC at 25° for 1 h gave the lactone (95) in excellent yield. By a similar sequence of reactions 96 was successfully converted to 97.

Synthesis of Japanese beetle pheromone²⁶: An useful application of this new methodology is exemplified with the synthesis of the Japanese beetle pheromone (104; Scheme 22)²⁶. Accordingly, the aldehyde (98) was treated with the lithium salt of 1-decyne (99) to obtain the acetylenic alcohol (100). Bromoetherification of 100 with NBS afforded the cyclic bromoether (101) which on subsequent treatment with potassium t-butoxide yielded the enol ether (102). In the crucial step, PCC oxidation of 102 effected a selective cleavage of the enol ether double bond to afford the lactone (103). Hydrogenation of 103 with Lindlar's catalyst afforded the Japanese beetle pheromone (±)-104²⁶.

Scheme 22

Acknowledgement

The author thanks all his students and associates for their contributions to the knowledge of the

methodologies reviewed in this article. The author is grateful to the Department of Science and Technology and Ministry of Defence, New Delhi for financial assistance of some phases of the work and to Mr. S. Baskaran for assistance in writing this article.

References

1. R. CRIGGER, *Ann.*, 1936, **522**, 75.
2. V. VAN REHENAN, R. C. KELLY and D. Y. CHA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1976, 1978.
3. H. J. SCHMIDT and H. J. SCHAFER, *Angew. Chem.*, 1979, **91**, 77; *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1979, **18**, 63.
4. T. SALA and M. V. SARGENT, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1978, 259.
5. J. A. MORRIS and D. C. MILLS, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1978, 446; J. JAGGER, J. LUTOLF and M. W. MEYER, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1979, **18**, 786; H. J. SCHMIDT and H. J. SCHAFER, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1979, **18**, 787.
6. V. BHUSHAN, R. RATHORE and S. CHANDRASEKARAN, *Synthesis*, 1984, 431.
7. R. RATHORE, V. BHUSHAN and S. CHANDRASEKARAN, *Chem. Lett.*, 1984, 2181.
8. T. K. CHAKRABORTY and S. CHANDRASEKARAN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1980, 1583; 1984, **25**, 2895.
9. T. K. CHAKRABORTY and S. CHANDRASEKARAN, *Chem. Lett.*, 1985, 551.
10. M. F. SCHLECT and H. J. KIM, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1985, **26**, 127.
11. W. C. BAILEY, A. K. BOSE, R. M. IKEDA, R. H. NEWMAN, H. V. SACOR and C. VARSEL, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, **33**, 2819.
12. T. L. HO, *Synth. Commun.*, 1974, **4**, 265.
13. (a) J. D. SHRINGAPURE and B. K. SABATA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **13**, 24; (b) U. KUCHIBOTLA, T. K. CHAKRABORTY and S. CHANDRASEKARAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, **23**, 1216.
14. R. RATHORE, P. S. VANKAR and S. CHANDRASEKARAN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1986, **27**, 4079.
15. F. D. BOUMECHAL, R. LORNE and G. LINSTRUMELLE, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1977, 1181. G. LINSTRUMELLE, H. LOME and H. P. DANG, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1978, 4069.
16. M. RAGHAVAN, M.Sc. Project Report, I. I. T., Kanpur, 1985.
17. P. S. VANKAR, R. RAM and S. CHANDRASEKARAN, unpublished results.
18. P. A. GRIECO and M. MIYASHITA, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1974, **39**, 120.
19. P. S. VANKAR and S. CHANDRASEKARAN, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1989, 000.
20. G. A. KRAUS and L. LANDGREBE, *Synthesis*, 1984, 885; R. S. MONSON, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1971, 113.
21. B. M. TROST, P. BUHLMAYER and M. MAO, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, 1443. B. M. TROST and M. J. BOGDANOWICZ, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 5321.
22. P. E. EATON and R. H. MUELLER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **94**, 1015.
23. S. DEV and C. RAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **34**, 266. F. COOKE, R. MOERCK, J. SCHWINDEMAN and P. MAGNUS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1980, **45**, 1046.
24. B. M. TROST and M. J. BOGDANOWICZ, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 6311.
25. D. W. BROOKS, P. G. GROTHOUS and W. L. IRWIN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1982, **47**, 2820.
26. E. KLEIN and W. ROJAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1965, **21**, 2853.
27. D. M. WALBA, M. D. WAND and M. C. WILKES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 4396.
28. J. E. BALDWIN, M. J. CROSSLEY and E. M. M. LEHTONEN, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1979, 918.
29. N. A. NOURELDIN and D. G. LEE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1982, **47**, 2790.
30. S. BASKARAN, I. ISLAM and S. CHANDRASEKARAN, unpublished results.

CHANDRASEKARAN : SUBSTITUENT DIRECTED OXIDATIVE CYCLISATION.

31. S. BASKARAN and S. CHANDRASEKARAN, unpublished results.
32. P. SUNDARARAMAN and W. HERZ, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1977, 42, 818.
33. G. PIANCATELLI, A. SCETTRI and M. D'AURIA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1977, 3483.
34. S. BASKARAN, I. ISLAM, M. RAGHAVAN and S. CHANDRASEKARAN, *Chem. Lett.*, 1987, 1175.
35. R. E. DEMOLE and P. ENGGIST, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1971, 54, 456.
36. I. ISLAM, S. BASKARAN and S. CHANDRASEKARAN, unpublished results.